

ON SOME ISSUES OF AUDIOVISUAL EDUCATION FOR EFL LEARNERS IN ARMENIAN SCHOOLS: SURVEY STUDY

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Abstract

The merit of this paper lies in the detailed exposition of some problems emerging in the process of applying audio-visual approach in the process of EFL learners in schools of Armenia.

Based on the analysis of the textbooks and the results of surveys conducted among the students of 27 schools in 3 regions of the Republic of Armenia, the following issues are addressed: firstly, the article details the demerits of school curriculum related to audiovisual materials in textbooks. Secondly, are presented the types of audiovisual materials: the intensity of implementing audio/video materials during the lesson, their impact on students' memory, and their role in enriching the learner's vocabulary. Thirdly, are revealed the existing technical, curriculum, classroom management and other problems, which reduce the effectiveness of implementing audiovisual education in public schools of the Republic of Armenia.

Keywords: audiovisual approach, audiovisual aids, memory study, vocabulary enrichment, listening and speaking comprehension, English textbooks.

Introduction

Foreign language acquisition and mastery contain complications for language learners. Lots of approaches, methods, and techniques have been developed to facilitate this process. Varying historical issues and circumstances are manifested in the changing classroom techniques and procedures used to teach a foreign language. Hence, we can mark changes in teaching approaches and methods as well (Richards J. C., Rodgers T. S. 2001). Some approaches develop contemporary methods or undergo modifications to meet the requirements of new educational environment. In other cases, some new approaches evolve, when the former ones do not justify themselves. This was the case of the audio-visual approach. In the modern world, the turn to audiovisual learning is inevitable and a holistic study is needed in the frame of the audiovisual approach.

In western countries, a lot of linguists have paid more attention to this audio-visual approach which connects sound with pictures and studied it. (Wang, 2009). *Audio-visual* (AV) learning is a type of learning which is characterized by the delivery and the use of instructional content that involves sound (auditory stimuli) and sight (visual stimuli). AV learning takes place when the instructional process is supplemented by AV learning aids such as flip charts, handouts, whiteboards, illustrations, still and motion pictures, slide shows, videos, television, audiotapes, projectors, records, computer graphics, and multimedia. AV learning can appear when an instructor's verbal presentation is bolstered with a series of images or slides or as a self-standing instructional practice consisting of an instructional movie or virtual reality simulation (Podolskiy, 2012).

Audiovisual materials, as American educator Edgar Dale (1900-1985) points out, permit an important

relationship to environmental events by providing direct operational definitions in which the operations directly represented by a symbol are made available for inspection. When the audio says "This is an elevator" and an elevator appears on the screen, the presentation provides a direct operational definition of the word elevator. The significance of such an experience is not just that it brings the student in touch with reality, but it provides him with a symbol that has an operational definition (Dale, 1960).

Audio-visual approach has proven to be highly productive in teaching a second language in the frame of other approaches and methods.

It's well acknowledged that there were already many positive reviews about the audiovisual approach, but alongside with good sides, several problems have prevented this new approach from being widely used in teaching process. Especially in the schools of the Republic of Armenia, the choice and application of audiovisual materials is left to the discretion of the teacher, as the textbooks do not contain proper audiovisual teaching materials.

When exploring the course books of Armenian schools we found out, that few listening and no video exercises were included in books. If we take high school course books only, the 10th-grade textbook includes solely 4 listening tasks for the whole academic year, 2 tasks are included in the 11th grade and 6 tasks in the 12th-grade textbooks.

It becomes obvious, that students do only 12 listening tasks during the entire 3 academic years. In addition, the fact that course books do not have supplementary video materials with their corresponding tasks is another hindrance to developing learners' skills profoundly.

Table 1.

Listening and Video materials included in RA English Textbooks

Coursebook Grade	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Listenings	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	2	6
Video	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

In most cases audiovisual materials included pictures, diagrams and the usage of different colors to make the pages of the book more attractive. This leads to the unbalanced development of the 4 basic language learning skills. Students develop reading and writing skills while listening and speaking skills remain deficient.

That is why we set a goal to find out the prevalence of audiovisual education in Armenian schools, the methods used, the obstacles that hinder the effectiveness of audiovisual learning.

Regarding the problems of audiovisual approach in Armenian schools and on the basis of the goal of the research, the following questions are proposed:

1. The main curriculum demerits concerning audiovisual materials
2. What the main types of problems concerning the use of audiovisual resources are
3. How effectively they are used

Research Method and Participants

We conducted the first stage of our research through surveys. The purpose of the survey is to determine the need and effectiveness of the audiovisual approach in foreign language teaching at schools. We accomplished the survey using Google Forms Online (See Note 1).³

The form was filled in by 158 students from a number of schools of the Republic of Armenia. Students took part in the experiment from different Regions: Shirak (5 schools), Armavir (5 schools) and Yerevan (19 schools). The choice of 3 regions allowed us to get a more holistic view from the results of the studies. The target group consisted of students of grades 9-12. 41% of the students surveyed are 9th graders (65 students), 8.9 % (14 students) are 10th graders, 18.4% (29 students) are of 11th grade and 31.6% (50 students) are of 12th grade.

Table 2.

Participants

Province	Schools	
Shirak Province (5 schools)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academic School, lyceum • 21 school 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 23 school • ShSU High School • Kamo Secondary School
Yerevan (17 schools)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School N93 • School N 83 after H.Galstyan • 94 High School after G. Margaryan • YSMU Herati high school • High school N 16 • High school N 139 • High school N 118 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High school N184 • School N 87 • N83 high school • High school N109 • School N 116 • School N31 • School N168 • School N 135 • School N192 • School N194
Armavir Region (5 schools)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vagharshapat High School N5 after Maxim Gorky • Nersisyan school N 6 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arshaluys school after S. Gri-goryan • School N8 • N5 School (Ashtarak)

One of our key tasks was to find out how are audio-visual materials distributed in their English language teaching process. The following options were introduced to the students: *pictures, cards, drawings and*

diagrams (Mind map, Venn diagram, etc.), posters, recordings, audio books, presentations, videos, movies (audio, silent, animation, etc.), cartoons and the option other.

³ Note 1

The link of the Online Survey which was used during the study:

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1fHvy-WXX9Nmp1KG3bxps736u2rG-xnL2XI3wG4gD6mI/edit>

Bar Chart 1. Distribution of Audiovisual Materials Used in Classroom Procedures

As it can be seen from the chart, mostly are used visual ones like pictures, cards drawings and posters. Recording, cartoons, videos, movies and audio books are inferior.

In the next step of the research we asked the students to rate the effectiveness of audiovisual materials over other traditional approaches, on the scale of 1-5.

Pie Chart 1. The effectiveness of audiovisual materials

74 % of students gave the maximum points to the effectiveness of audiovisual materials. 21 % of them gave the second highest mark to audiovisual materials i.e. 4. Only 8 students out of 158 gave 2 or 3 low marks and none of the participants gave the lowest mark i.e. 1.

According to the obtained results we can see that most of the students consider audiovisual materials as an efficient tool for making their lessons more productive.

The question below is strongly related to the previous one:

“Does your interest in the lesson increase when the teacher uses different audiovisual materials in class?”

147 students stated that audiovisual materials made lessons more stimulating and effective.

11 of them picked the option ‘not so much’. None of them mentioned ‘no’. This is a two-fold question as it firstly states, that audiovisual materials make the lesson more motivating and make students get involved in the lesson easily. Secondly, it reveals several drawbacks of audiovisual materials that interfere some students to consider audiovisual materials as great stimulators for studying.

The second part of our form refers to auditory materials and their necessity for developing listening skills. At first we tried to find out the prevalence of accomplishing exercises that are linked with recordings. Before introducing the results of the questions, it is worth mentioning that school textbooks do not contain any audio recording and don’t have their own CDs or other online sources which are related to the development of listening skills. Moreover, the recordings are not often favourable as are chosen by teachers themselves and are left to their discretion.

Our first question concerning listening is: *“How often do you do listening tasks during the lessons?”*. 18% of the students (28 students) mentioned that they accomplish listening tasks 2-3 times a week. 35% of them chose the second option i.e. 3-5 times a month. It means once a week.

28 students i.e. the other 18% of them claim, that they do listening tasks 4-5 times during the semester or once a month. And the rest i.e. 29 percent of them is sure that they either do listening tasks rarely or don’t accomplish it at all.

How Often Do You Do Listening Tasks During The Lessons?

Pie Chart 2. The Frequency of Using Listenings at Schools

Only 18% of respondents claim that they perform listening tasks at least 1-2 times a week.

As already mentioned, textbooks up to the 9th grade do not provide assignments and tasks intended to develop listening comprehension of the students. The development of auditory skills requires long-term gradual development, which should start with small steps.

This ratio of answers is worded in the next question. Answering the next question "Do you have difficulties understanding native speakers? If so, what do you think is the reason?" most students answered that they have problems understanding English speech without any subtitles or another helping material. 25 of them think they don't have problem with understanding English when listening. The other 133 students think

they face problems when they try to comprehend unfamiliar speech in English. Several reasons can lead to this problem.

- The *first* one is connected with speech pace.
- The *second* reason is the lack of experience:
- The *third* reason is that in teaching/learning process we draw much more attention on the other aspects of language than on listening:
 - The *fourth* reason is connected with the predominance of visual memory over auditory:
 - The *fifth* reason relates to the lack of necessary concentration. Thus concentration should be aroused by interesting materials.

The third part of our form refers to the efficiency of visual materials for teaching/learning vocabulary much more effectively.

Op-	Op-
	<p>Break - կոտրել Melt - հալվել Spread - տարածել Roll out - գրտնակել Peel - կլպել Mix - հարել Whip - հարել Fry - տապակել Saute - տապակել Grate - քերել</p>
	<p>○ Option 1 ○ Option 2 ○ 2 options together</p>

77 (48.7%) students stated they would prefer blending of 2 options together as pictures and Armenian translations together helped them to master the language in a more holistic way. 63 students preferred the first option of studying as pictures helped them to understand the phenomena with great ease. For example, in the Armenian language the words *mix* and *whip* are translated in the same way, while it is quite visible

from option one that they show different actions implying different meanings. The same is for *fry* and *saute*. And 18 students (11.4%) prefer only translations as they feel themselves more comfortable with adequate translations.

With the help of the next question, we tried to reveal what ratio of audiovisual materials is desirable for students.

Տարբերակ 1 Ներկա շարունակական ժամանակաձևը կազմվում է to be բայի խոնարհված ձևերի և ing-ային վերջավորություն ունեցող բայի միջոցով:

Տարբերակ 2 Ներկա շարունակական ժամանակաձևը կազմվում է՝
to be (խոնարհված՝ am, is are) + Verbing:

Տարբերակ 3 Ներկա շարունակական ժամանակաձևը կազմվում է՝

I	Am	Playing
You	Are	
He She It	Is	Dancing Singing Eating

Ex. I am playing a new intellectual game.
You are working on a new project.
He is eating out at the moment.

- Option 1
- Option 2
- Option 3
- I would prefer a video that presents the material in details

In the first option the material is presented in the native language. The second option is quite similar to the first one but it is flavored with colors. The third option is quite different from the first ones as it includes colors, diagrams, additional information on the topic presented mostly in English. And the 4th option is a

video that represents the material with the help of interesting animations, and is accompanied by an explanatory speech in English. The video created by us contains all visual and auditory components. Here are the results of the questionnaire of students:

Pie Chart 3. Results of Question N11

As we can see from the following diagram, students chose mostly the 3rd and the 4th options, which contained most audiovisual components. Similarly, 94.3 percent of students answered *yes* to the question: ‘Would you like your lessons to be mostly accompanied by instructional videos?’ And 5.7 percent of them answered ‘Not so much’.

Trying to understand how audiovisual materials help students to develop their memory was posed our penultimate question “Do audiovisual materials help you to remember what you have studied?”. Students state that audiovisual materials help them to retain the information in their memory for a long time.

And the aim of our final question is to find out the obstacles that can be encountered during audiovisual learning. Considering the answers given by the students we can outline the following problems:

Technical problems (equipment (computers, speakers), bad internet connection) - no matter how much we talk about the use of audio-visual materials, especially audio and video materials, we cannot ignore the fact that in Armenian schools there is a must for appropriate equipment for running, listening or watching

such materials. Hence, we can state that merely the availability of materials cannot solve this problem and appropriate technical conditions are essential. One of the most commonly used solutions is to conduct the lesson in the school's computer classrooms.

Attention focus – In some cases, audiovisual materials help students to focus their attention on the material, in other cases it can distract their attention from the main lesson. Teachers should help their students and instruct them to get involved in the lesson. They should arouse their interest in the video with questions or a preface. This is one of the possible preconditions.

Problems of choosing the wrong material (teachers may choose inappropriate material (for example a boring video that is not linked with the main aim of the lesson, or a video that is hard to understand). As the choice of audio-video materials is left to the discretion of the teachers, it can lead to several problems.

1. The selected video may be interesting but of no relation to the lesson. In this case, the children will watch the video, but it will not help them to summarize or reinforce the knowledge they have achieved from the

textbook. In terms of developing language skills, educational video clips are more productive and efficient when they are of a complementary and reinforcing nature.

This experience is quite nicely displayed in the international textbooks of general English teaching,

where the book units are divided into 4-5 sub-units. Audio materials start from the very first subunit and they gradually become more complicated. The video materials are left in the last sub-chapters, summarizing the whole material and they are strictly related to the topic.

Table 3.

International English Textbooks: Comparison

	Unit	Recordings	Videos	
English File (Elementary) <i>Authors: Latham-Koenig C., Lambert J, 2019</i>	Unit 8	8A (A Murder Mystery)	8	-
		8B (A House with a Mystery)	7	-
		8C (Room 333)	2	1 (A haunted Castle)
SpeakOut (Staretr) <i>Authors: Eales F., Oakes S. 2016</i>	Unit 9 Shopping	9.1 (A Waste of Money)	3	-
		9.2 (the Right Gift)	1	-
		9.3 (I'D Like A...)	5	-
		9.4 (The Borrowing Shop)	1	1 (Leila, the 'borrowing shop')
		9.5 (Lookback)	-	-

This experience can be successfully applied in Armenian curriculum. Of course, age characteristics and language skills must be taken into account.

2. The teacher can find a video that is relevant to the topic, but it can be difficult to understand or confusing. Hence, a systematic approach is needed.

Lesson control and time management

Time management is a very important factor. Watching videos or doing related tasks should not be an end in itself. The use of audiovisual materials takes extra time from lesson and teachers should be able to manage the time. This process must be coherently organized and planned in advance.

To sum up, according to the results of our survey we found out that there isn't a proper usage of audiovisual materials in language learning process in Armenian schools. In most cases students consider audiovisual aids as a good means of making their listening and speaking skills better, but a proper attention should be given to the selected materials. It should be in line with the lesson and the level of English. The 4 main problems include technical ones, problems of choosing the wrong material, attention focus and time management. Thus, an innovative and systematic attention is needed in the frame of audio-visual materials in the curriculum.

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